

Consequences of Cultism in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria as Perceived by Undergraduates of the Delta State University, Abraka

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Abstract

This study investigated how students perceive the consequences of cultism in schools based on their gender and duration at school. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted the descriptive survey design. The population study comprised 13,134 undergraduates in Delta State University, Abraka. A sample of 300 undergraduates drawn randomly from the six faculties in Abraka campus i.e., faculties of arts, Basic Medical Sciences, Education, Science, Pharmacy and sciences were used for the study. The study used a questionnaire to gather data on the consequence of cultism. Frequency counts and rank order was used to answer the research questions while the t-test was determined and was used to test the null hypotheses tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance. The study found that insecurity on campus and of cult members, sexual harassment among students, examination malpractice and blood-letting are perceived as the most common consequences of cultism on campus; and that there is no difference in the perception of male and female undergraduates as well as fresh and stale undergraduates on the consequences of cultism on campus. The study recommended that orientation programs should be organized for students both fresh and stale on regular basis in which the consequences of cultism of campus are highlighted.

Keywords: Cultism; Tertiary Institutions; Undergraduates; Examination Malpractice.

Introduction

One problem that has dominated discussions among educationists in Nigeria in recent times is violence in schools. There was school shooting at columbine High school, USA in 1999. Mason Angela, a school teacher was suspended for uncovering violence in schools in London and Birmingham in 2007. According to 2001 polls on school safety in America (Gallop 2001), the apparently random nature of school violence has raised public fears to epidemic proportion that between 50 to 75% of parents of school children thinks that violence can occur in any school within the American society.

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In Nigeria, it was thought that disruptive and violent behaviors of students in schools was a strange phenomenon in educational system but regarded only as an American, European or Asian educational syndrome. The reason behind this was that the Nigerian child was so well brought up and could not defy the authority of the elder-statesman, the teacher. According to Ehiematalor (1981), all of these have eroded with the occurrences of violence in the Nigerian school environment. Nigerians were shocked when newspapers reported in September, 2010 the kindergarten and primary school children were kidnapped in Abia State. There was also a report of bomb blast in October 1st, 2010 at Abuja during Nigeria's 50th Independence Day celebration. Violence in the schools therefore seems to be mirroring violence in the society.

Ikoya (2004) strongly opined that societal crimes have impact on school violence and crime. Rotimi (2005) also implicated social change in the Nigerian society as an agent of violence in Nigeria schools. He therefore traced these violence to include bloody military coups which dominated Nigeria from 1966 to 1993, the bloody civil war of 1967-1970, politically related assassinations, domestic violence and the menace of ethnic militias such as the odua people's congress (OPC) in the south-west of Nigeria, the Bakassi Boys and movement of the actualization of the sovereign state of Biafra (MASSOB) in the south-eastern part of Nigerian; the Arewa Youth Forum and its affiliation to religious extremism such as Boko haram, sharia etc. in the northern part of Nigeria and the Niger-delta militants involved in hostage taking bombing of pipelines and disruption of oil prospecting activities in the south-south region of Nigeria. Rotimi (2005) concluded that the most catalytic agent of violence in Nigerian schools is the recent cult phenomenon.

According to him secret cults have perpetrated gruesome murder in the Nigeria institutions of learning and that from 1981 when the earliest secret cult violence was reported in the university of Lagos, so many cases of murder, other forms of violence and disruption of school calendar have been witnessed in schools. According to him in 1991, a student in the university of Port Harcourt was beheaded by rival cult murders, cult clashes also led to the death of a principal assistant registrar of Delta State University, Abraka while on 10th July, 1999, five students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife were killed in cult violence. in 2002, two students of the university of Jos were shot dead in their sleep during the miss “unijos” competitions (shobayo, 2002). The list of secret cult clashes, terrorism and violence on campus is endless. Of course, secret cult wars have been reported in the society. They are being glorified so that their prevalence and their activities in school mirror what exists in the society (Oyewo, et al, 2007) said that cultism which is now common in our tertiary institutions of learning is a common phenomenon charactering our society. To him, cultism is a social crime and that various governments both states and federal and individual school authorities have made series of attempts at checking and controlling their existence and activities especially in the higher institutions of learning.

Some of the measures included decree 47 of 1989 which specified jail term ranging from 7-21 years for being convicted as a member of a cult, expulsion and rustication of cult members from school and the recent being renunciation, a kind of amnesty being granted to members by the authority of the institution. According to (oyewo, et al 2007), apart from consequences of cultism in the school environment, the various meetings, activities and initiation rites for members have become increasingly complex and shrouded in mysteries. Meetings are held in obscure places at odd times particularly at night while initiation rites

have become more and more barbaric and bizarre and the oath, compelled to the taken by members have become a serious threat to life in a normal society and the school environment. This is of great concern to parents, teachers and society generally.

According to Ndaaji (1997) secret cult membership exposes the students to indulging in the use of hard drugs, blood-letting, rape, violence, tendencies to contracting AIDS, rebelliousness to parents and untimely death. Their activities also create insecurity in the school environment. Students appear to be sitting on a keg of gun powder and therefore unrelaxed because of cults and cult related problems on campuses (Oyewo, et al 2007). Another consequence of cultism in school is the destruction and loss of school property as well as disruption of school related activities such as social and political activities, examination and academic activities and the calendar year. It is against this background that this study seeks to examine the consequences of cultism as perceived by students.

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, the activities of secret cult members in institutions on higher learning in Nigeria have assumed a very dangerous dimension that the society at large is no more comfortable when the word “cult” is mentioned. Parents have lost their money and their beloved children in schools. Some students have been killed, disfigured, maimed, brutalized and terrorized in schools. Students have also abandoned their studies in order to avoid being terrorized. According to Ndaaji (1997), secret cult membership exposes the student to indulgence in the use of hard drugs, blood-letting, rape, violence, tendencies to contracting AIDS, rebelliousness to parents, demanding money from parents, uncles and extorting or stealing from other people as well as untimely death.

As a result of the horrific activities of cultism, many students and lecturers now live in fear and have emotional problems, which prevent them from serious academic exercise. Cultism in schools have led to the prevalence of academic injustice as lecturers either for fear of being attacked or are members of one of the cults may award marks in favour of cult members at the detriment of hard working and industrious students (Asafa, 1991). Previous studies have focused on causes and prevalence of cultism in schools. Very few studies are available in the literature on the consequence of cultism in tertiary institutions as perceived by students. The problem of this study is how do undergraduates perceive the consequence of cultism in the school and on members?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. Is there any gender difference among undergraduates in their perception of the consequences of cultism?
2. Is there any difference in the perception of fresh and stale undergraduates of the consequences of cultism?

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: there is no statistically significant difference in the perception of male and female undergraduates of the consequences of cultism

Ho₂: there is no statistically significant differences in the perception of fresh and stale undergraduates of the consequences of cultism

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out how students based on their gender and duration at school, perceive the consequences of cultism in schools.

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Significance of the Study

Result of the study shall be of benefit to students, administrators, parents, members of the society, stake holders and counselors. Outcomes of the study will help them to understand or become better aware of the consequences of students' involvement in cultism in higher schools. This is likely to help to reduce lure to become members.

Research Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey design which according to Ofo (2001) involves collection of data from a defined population to describe variables under survey or study. This also meets the position of stangor (2004) that the purpose of descriptive research is to describe systematically the facts and characteristics of a given population and area of interest, factually and accurately.

Sample and sampling procedure

The population of the study comprised of all the undergraduates in Delta State University, Abraka. The figure is 13, 134 as at June 2010 academic year (Academic Planning Unit, Delsu 2010). A sample of 300 undergraduates drawn randomly from the six faculties in Abraka campus i.e., faculties of arts, Basic Medical Sciences, Education, Science, Pharmacy and sciences were used for the study.

Instrumentation

The study used a questionnaire to gather data on the consequence of cultism. It was constructed by (Ayena, et al 2010) and tagged consequences of cultism questionnaire (COCQ). The instrument is divided into two sections, A and B. section a deal with the personal data of respondent such as gender, duration in school i.e. fresh or stale, religion,

residence i.e. off or on campus and type of institution i.e. polytechnic, university, college of education or school of nursing or agriculture etc.

Section B contains 20 item that measure various types of consequence of cultism in school such as physical consequences, psychological consequences, emotional consequences, economic consequences and social consequences. The instrument was validated to have face content and construct validity by five experts in counseling and psychology. Again the 20 items were subjected to internal consistency analysis. The reliability index of the instrument was ascertained by the measure of stability obtained from a sample of 40 students (20 males and 20 females) who were not part of the target population. The cronbach Alpha formula was used to ascertain the homogeneity of the rating scale. Mean scores were used in analyzing the response and the cronbach alpha co-efficient value of 0.69 was obtained which indicated a satisfactory co-efficient to measure stability reliability.

Respondent are to rate items on a four-point scale ranging from strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed and strongly Disagreed.

Administration of the instrument

The instrument was administered by the researcher assisted by trained students to 50 sampled undergraduates from each of the six faculties in Abraka campus of the Delta State University. The instruments were collected as soon as a respondent finished or completed it

Data Analysis

The frequency count for each of the items in the instrument was recorded and the mean score were calculated and ranked accordingly. The frequency counts and rank order

was used to answer the research questions while the t-test was determined and was used to test the null hypotheses tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

The result of data analysis on the consequences of cultism in schools as perceived by undergraduates in delta State University Abraka Campus is presented below.

Table 1 showing perception of undergraduates on the consequences of cultism in tertiary institutions according to frequencies, percentages and rank order.

Item No On Questionnaire	Consequences of cultism	Frequency	percent age	Rank Order
2	Insecurity of cult members	270	90	1 st
6	Sexual harassment among students	270	90	1 st
13	Closure of institution as a result of cult wars/rampage	270	90	1 st
15	Cult members get involved in various forms of examination malpractice	268	89.3	4 th
3	Murder and blood-letting	260	86.6	5 th
9	Extorting money from fellow students	259	86.3	6 th
12	False collection of money from parents	258	86	7 th
4	Innocent students fall prey to cult member	258	86	7 th

	(rapes, intimidation etc)			
14	Suspension and rustication of cult members from school	257	85.6	9 th
16	Distraction of students attention from academic work	257	85.6	9 th
18	Cult members become drug addicts	253	84.3	11 th
8	Cult members become riotous and have no respect for public property	252	84	12 th
1	The loss of personal identity by cult members	240	80	13 th
7	An individual becoming mentally ill	228	76	14 th
5	Destruction of life and family values	228	76	14 th
19	Members of cults are sometimes ostracized from society	221	73.6	16 th
10	Destruction of valuable property e.g. cars, houses, signposts	220	73.3	17 th
20	Members find it difficult to marry	218	72.6	18 th
11	Highway robbery, bank robbery, armed robbery, robbing of houses	215	71.6	19 th
17	Cult members resort to barbaric and retrogressive behavior tendencies that rob them of chances to be future leaders and responsible citizens	200	66.6	20 th

The table shows that items 3, 6 & 13 on the questionnaire i.e. insecurity of cult members, sexual harassment among students and closure of institution as a result of violent cult wars or clashes were perceived to be the most popular consequences of cultism in schools followed closely by involvement of cult members in various forms of examination malpractices and murder and blood-letting. Items 17, 11 and 20 respectively were perceived to be the least consequences of cultism in schools. Generally, respondents agreed to the consequences of cultism in schools as described by items on the questionnaire.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no statistical significant difference between males and female undergraduates in their perception of consequences of cultism in schools.

Table 11 showing means, standard deviation and t-value of respondents on the consequences of cultism according to gender.

variables	N	Means (\bar{X})	SD	DF	Calculated t-value	Table t-value
males	140	64.75	7.85	298	1.78	1.96
Females	160	64.25	7.05			

p>0.05

the result shows that the calculated t-value of 1.78 is less than the critical value of 1.96 the null hypothesis of no significant gender difference in the perception of undergraduates of the

consequences of cultism is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between male and female undergraduates in their perception of the consequences of cultism in schools.

Hypothesis Two

Ho₁: there is no statistical significant difference in the perception of fresh and stale undergraduates of the consequences of cultism in schools.

Table 11 showing the means, standard deviation and t-values of fresh and stale students in their perception of consequences of cultism in schools.

Status of student by duration on campus	N	Means (\bar{X})	SD	DF	Calculated t-value	Table t- value
fresh	120	63.5	8.83	298	1.42	1.96
stale	160	63.15	9.17			

The result shows that the calculated t-value of 1.42 is less than the critical t-value of 1.96. the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the perception of fresh and stale undergraduates of the consequences of cultism in schools.

Discussion

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From the analysis of data, it was clear that students perceived all the items on the questionnaires as consequences of cultism in schools, although at various degrees. The fact that insecurity on campus and of cult members, sexual harassment among students, examination malpractice and blood-letting are perceived as the most common consequences of cultism on campus is not surprising. These consequences have been attested to in the literature (Asafa, 1991; Adekeye, 1997; Fawole, 2002; Oyewo, et al, 2007).

Again, it was found that there is no difference in the perception of male and female undergraduates as well as fresh and stale undergraduates on the consequences of cultism on campus. Of course, students irrespective of gender are aware of the activities of cults on campus. Both fresh and stale students also know the terrorist and horrific activities of cults on campus. Both fresh and stale students also know the terrorist and horrific activities of cults on campus. Of course, Chibisi, (1997) reported that there are cults for male only just as there are for females only. Thus there is so much awareness across gender about the activities of cults on campuses. Furthermore, newspapers are full with reports of cult activities on campus. Cult activities have also dominated discussions at home and the society. There are also the activities of cults in the society and even in secondary schools (Chibisi, 1997; Ndaoji, 1997). All these have created awareness among undergraduates irrespective of whether they are male, female, fresh or stale students about the activities and consequences of cultism on campus.

Recommendations

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The following recommendations are put forward as a way of checking the consequences of cultism on campus.

- i. Orientation programs should be organized for students both fresh and stale on regular basis in which the consequences of cultism of campus are highlighted
- ii. Guidance and counseling Centre's should be established in campuses to resolve matters of socio-personal nature that otherwise would lure students to be cult members.
- iii. School authorities should sanction those members be it staff or students who openly wear or display cult symbols, slogans and paraphernalia on campus.
- iv. Government should revamp exchange programs in which students have opportunity to study in universities in affiliated countries under sponsorship. Beneficiaries should not be students suspected to be cult members.

Conclusion

the study found that undergraduates irrespective of gender and number of years spent on campus perceived the consequences of cultism as horrific and capable of bringing about insecurity for both members and innocent students on campus. It was recommended among others that there should be counseling Centre's in all schools and that there should be orientation for all students at the beginning of a new session. Orientation should emphasize appropriate values and consequences of cultism on campus. School authority should take measures to check cultism by sanctioning members and staff who openly display on campus paraphernalia, symbols, logos and slogans of cult groups.

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